

Sample Name: dNMPs 400uM -P-1 50x

```

=====
Acq. Operator   : SYSTEM                      Seq. Line :    4
Sample Operator : SYSTEM
Acq. Instrument : HPLC-UV-FC                 Location  :    4
Injection Date  : 1/8/2021 1:15:01 PM        Inj       :    1
                                           Inj Volume: 50.000 µl
Method          : C:\Users\Public\Documents\ChemStation\3\Data\dNMP to dNTP yield 2021-01-08
                  11-55-26\dNTP QUANTIFICATION.M (Sequence Method)
Last changed    : 12/10/2020 6:09:05 PM by SYSTEM
=====

```



```

=====
Fraction Information
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No Fractions found.
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Area Percent Report
=====

```

```

Sorted By      :      Signal
Multiplier     :      1.0000
Dilution      :      1.0000
Do not use Multiplier & Dilution Factor with ISTDs

```

Signal 1: VWD1 A, Wavelength=254 nm

Peak #	RetTime [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area [mAU*s]	Height [mAU]	Area %
1	1.879	VB R	0.0889	18.52968	2.90903	0.8854
2	2.080	BV	0.0591	39.02991	10.22051	1.8650
3	2.247	VB	0.0609	16.93093	4.01383	0.8090
4	2.409	BV	0.0840	14.04852	2.41069	0.6713
5	2.592	VV R	0.1021	35.27623	5.03538	1.6857
6	8.293	BB	0.2093	30.09226	2.32421	1.4379

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                : 11-55-26\DNTP QUANTIFICATION.M (Sequence Method)
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=====
```

Peak #	RetTime [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area [mAU*s]	Height [mAU]	Area %
7	9.776	BB	0.1733	19.89126	1.75071	0.9505
8	10.459	BV	0.1793	201.91759	17.18670	9.6485
9	10.904	VB	0.1751	44.12265	3.79078	2.1084
10	12.929	BV R	0.1767	373.99484	32.45370	17.8712
11	13.458	VB E	0.1831	50.65649	4.19537	2.4206
12	14.776	BB	0.1852	254.82079	21.00196	12.1765
13	16.259	BB	0.1854	488.36932	40.21662	23.3365
14	18.436	BB	0.1912	505.04727	40.34680	24.1334

Totals : 2092.72773 187.85629

```
=====
*** End of Report ***
```